

**PREVENTING CRIME AGAINST ANIMALS: A REVIEW OF
EFFECTIVE SITUATIONAL PREVENTION APPROACHES**

Prevención de delitos contra los animales: una revisión de enfoques eficaces de prevención situacional

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ABSTRACT

The impact of animal cruelty extends to the physical and emotional well-being of animals, the effectiveness of conservation efforts, and the safety of people. The article aims to investigate situational strategies that may prevent animal cruelty and conduct a comprehensive evaluation of their efficacy in reducing offenses against animals. This research employs a comprehensive approach by gathering data from many sources, such as peer-reviewed journals, papers, and books. The study investigates several situational preventative strategies, such as strengthening targets, limiting access, surveillance, altering the environment, implementing regulations, and supervising offenders. Employing situational preventative approaches shows promise in tackling instances of animal cruelty. However, the successful implementation of these restrictions requires a coordinated and varied approach that involves collaboration between law enforcement, government bodies, and conservation organizations.

Keywords: Preventing crime, wildlife crime, environmental design, target hardening.

RESUMEN

El impacto de la crueldad animal se extiende al bienestar físico y emocional de los animales, la eficacia de los esfuerzos de conservación y la seguridad de las personas. El artículo tiene como objetivo investigar estrategias situacionales que puedan prevenir la crueldad animal y realizar una evaluación integral de su eficacia para reducir los delitos contra los animales. Esta investigación emplea un enfoque integral mediante la recopilación de datos de muchas fuentes, como revistas revisadas por pares, artículos y libros. El estudio investiga varias estrategias preventivas situacionales, como el fortalecimiento de los objetivos, la limitación del acceso, la vigilancia, la alteración del medio ambiente, la implementación de regulaciones y la supervisión de los infractores. El empleo de enfoques preventivos situacionales muestra ser prometedor para abordar los casos de crueldad animal. Sin embargo, la implementación exitosa de estas restricciones requiere un enfoque coordinado y variado que involucre la colaboración entre las fuerzas de seguridad, los organismos gubernamentales y las organizaciones de conservación.

Palabras claves: Prevención del delito, delitos contra la vida silvestre, diseño ambiental, endurecimiento de objetivos.

INTRODUCTION

Poaching, trafficking, and the devastation of animal habitats are just some of the many forms of animal crime that have risen to prominence in recent years. This kind of crime has far-reaching detrimental effects on ecosystems and the environment as a whole, in addition to having devastating effects on individual creatures. As a result, a growing body of literature is dedicated to studying ways to reduce animal crime [1], [2].

Around 35,000 incidences of animal cruelty were recorded in India in 2019, according to data collected by the country's National Crime Records Bureau. In 2019, rural crime, which includes crimes against animals, including theft and unlawful hunting, was predicted to cost the UK agricultural business £54 million, according to the National Farmers' Union [3].

According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, the yearly value of the illicit wildlife trade is between \$7 billion and \$23 billion.

Poaching and illegal hunting are the most prevalent wildlife-related offenses, according to a study by the National Park Service in 2017 [4].

According to research by the Humane Society of the United States, up to 71% of victims of a domestic violence claim that their abuser also attacked their pets [5].

The aspiration to prioritize the well-being of the people and the increasing accumulation of information on animal welfare have prompted efforts to develop more effective methods to protect animals from mistreatment. This academic debate extends beyond the mere implementation of legal frameworks and encompasses a holistic approach that integrates educational initiatives, community engagement, policy advancements, and policy innovation. This article

seeks to evaluate the effectiveness and possible future advancements of situational preventative techniques in the field of animal welfare by referring to prominent papers and current articles.

The research operates on the premise that occurrences of animal welfare violations are intricate and need a complete approach for successful prevention. Hawkins and Williams [6] emphasized the significance of commencing early in the instruction of nonhuman animals to primary school pupils, as this establishes the foundation for further investigations into the efficacy of such initiatives. This approach posits that the future social perception and significance attributed to animal welfare will be significantly influenced by individuals' views towards animals throughout their formative years and early adulthood.

Velarde et al. [7] provided a significant addition to the discourse on animal welfare by examining the ecological sustainability of animal production systems. Their study underscores the need for industrial approaches that prioritize the emotional and physical well-being of animals, in line with broader ecological and ethical goals regarding consumption. It is crucial to develop specific preventive methods to address animal welfare concerns in agricultural contexts, taking into account these considerations.

Hampton, Warburton, and Sandøe [8] question commonly held beliefs on conservation by analyzing the consequences and humane approaches of conservation measures. Their methodology challenges long-standing conservation beliefs and advocates for a solution that safeguards both the ecological balance and the welfare of individual animals. Incorporating this perspective is crucial for the re-evaluation of conservation endeavors in order to protect the biodiversity of ecosystems and mitigate the risk of species extinction.

The increasing acknowledgment and observance of the rights and well-being of animals is shown in the broadening of regulations against cruelty to include animals employed in research [9]. The growing use of empathic approaches in research is indicative of a broader societal inclination to protect and recognize the intrinsic value of all living entities.

In addition, the study conducted by Wolf and Hamilton [10] investigates the administration of free-roaming cats, offering a valuable understanding of the challenges associated with urban animal welfare and emphasizing the need for public and community engagement in tackling these issues. Their work elucidates community-driven strategies for managing urban animal populations, which include the social and ecological dynamics of cities, as well as animal welfare.

This article seeks to combine several research approaches to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the effectiveness of situational preventative methods in the domain of animal welfare. This research aims to elucidate how society might bolster the safeguarding of animals from transgressions and maltreatment by taking into account legal, educational, ethical, and community-based perspectives. By doing this, it seeks to provide an intellectual addition to the discourse on animal welfare and preventative efforts.

1.1 The study objective

This article examines the efficacy of situational preventative tactics in reducing animal-related crime. The paper will summarize effective measures such as target hardening, access control, surveillance, environmental management, regulation, and offender management by synthesizing data from various sources. This article will examine the efficacy of these methods for lowering animal-related crime rates and highlight

the need for a unified, multi-faceted strategy that includes a wide range of interested parties. The study will also stress the need for further studies to learn more about the effects of situational prevention techniques and find alternative ways to lessen animal cruelty.

1.2. Problem statement

Cruelty to animals has a substantial detrimental influence not only on the well-being of animals but also on public safety and the success of conservation initiatives. Even though more people are aware of this problem, the number of crimes involving animals is still relatively high, and we need to develop more effective preventative techniques. There need to be more extensive studies on the effectiveness and implementation of situational preventive measures, although these approaches have shown promise in decreasing crime. Therefore, it is vital to examine and synthesize the existing knowledge on situational preventative strategies to prevent crimes committed against animals and to pinpoint areas where further research and development are needed.

BACKGROUND: A REVIEW OF EFFECTIVE SITUATIONAL PREVENTION APPROACHES

An integrated strategy is required to address the complex interaction of elements that have been described in the literature addressing the prevention of offenses against animals. However, some shortcomings and challenges persist in many research efforts, highlighting the need for innovative solutions and broader incorporation of findings into practical applications.

Hawkins and Williams highlight the capacity of educational interventions to foster empathy for animals in primary school pupils. Nevertheless, there needs to be more studies examining the successful implementation

of these attitudes into long-lasting behavioral changes. The presence of this lack of understanding suggests the need for a long-term study to ascertain if educational impacts endure and to devise additional strategies that strengthen learned habits over an individual's lifespan [6].

The study done by Velarde et al. highlights the importance of animal well-being in agricultural methods for the sustainable production of swine meat. However, economic constraints sometimes take precedence over ethical concerns in the global livestock production industry, hindering the broad adoption of animal welfare techniques. Possible solutions include implementing policy incentives to encourage the adoption of procedures that promote animal welfare, as well as launching consumer education campaigns to stimulate demand for meat that is produced ethically [7].

The prioritization of species conservation above individual animal well-being is a recurring ethical dilemma that often hinders conservation efforts, as explored by Hampton, Warburton, and Sande. This issue needs to be addressed in the creation of frameworks that successfully integrate concepts of compassionate conservation with biodiversity management. Collaborative study between conservationists and animal welfare professionals may uncover innovative strategies that protect both the balance of ecosystems and the well-being of animals [8].

Childers investigates the implementation of measures to prevent animal abuse in scientific research, providing insights into the evolving ethical standards that regulate research methods. However, there still needs to be a significant discrepancy in the broad adoption of these standards, particularly in regions with less stringent regulatory systems. This disparity may be improved by fostering international collaboration and implementing worldwide standards for animal experimentation [9].

According to the analysis conducted by Wolf and Hamilton, the management of free-roaming cats may be seen as a prototype for community-driven animal welfare projects. Nevertheless, there needs to be more advancement in the broader use of these models to resolve conflicts between human populations and urban wildlife. Researching scalable and flexible community participation approaches might effectively solve the issues of urban wildlife management [10].

In his study, Rodriguez Ferrere investigates the widespread problem of insufficient implementation of legislation pertaining to the well-being of animals, as shown in existing scholarly works. This issue underscores the need for strengthened legal frameworks, more robust enforcement mechanisms, and heightened public awareness to ensure that the law is not only adequate but also effectively implemented. Enhancing the enforcement, adherence, and documentation of animal cruelty instances might be enhanced by fostering cooperation among animal welfare groups, law enforcement agencies, and the community [11].

In addition, Chaves et al. have investigated the possibility of disease transmission in wildlife rehabilitation centers, revealing a lack of effective biosecurity measures and disease control procedures in place at these institutions. Implementing uniform biosecurity practices in wildlife rehabilitation clinics via staff and volunteer training might decrease the probability of disease spread to local wildlife populations [12].

This review utilizes contemporary academic works to provide insight into the intricate difficulties and possible solutions pertaining to animal welfare. It specifically focuses on the significance of community engagement, enforcement strategies, shelter management, and ethical handling of animals.

Moss et al. highlight the importance of community participation in animal control and field services, suggesting that officers and the communities they serve may achieve more compassionate and efficient solutions to animal welfare issues via better collaboration and communication [13]. This study emphasizes the need for animal welfare NGOs to develop robust public relations strategies in order to enhance public understanding and support for animal welfare programs.

In this study, Morton et al. investigate the disparity between the public's expectations and the actual capacities of law enforcement in enforcing animal welfare laws in Australia. This mismatch highlights the need to educate the public on the scope of animal welfare laws and the challenges faced by enforcement authorities. This education is necessary to bridge the gap between public expectations and reality [14].

Koralesky, Rankin, and Fraser elaborate on the concept of "One Welfare" in relation to the preservation and defense of animals, advocating for an approach that considers the well-being of both the animals and the people involved in animal welfare situations [15]. This perspective emphasizes the need to consider the well-being of both animals and shelter workers, as well as the communities they live in. It highlights the interconnection between the well-being of humans and animals.

Lorászko et al. have brought attention to a disparity between police statistics and the perspectives of animal welfare non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in Hungary with regard to the issue of animal cruelty. The disparity between the act of reporting and the way it is perceived may hinder the capacity of law enforcement and animal welfare groups to cooperate efficiently. Through joint activities and pooled training programs, we can enhance the effective-

ness of efforts to eliminate animal abuse [16].

Horecka and Neal identify notable obstacles that afflict the domain of animal sheltering research, such as the need for defined procedures and outcome metrics [17]. The presence of this research gap suggests that collaborative efforts are necessary to establish uniform standards for evaluating shelter operations and outcomes, eventually resulting in an improvement in the quality of care given to animals in shelters.

Hurley examines the changing role of triage and appointment-based admissions in animal shelters and presents a paradigm that might improve animal service, treatment, and results. This approach emphasizes the potential for operational improvements in shelter management to enhance both animal well-being and operational efficiency [18].

In publication, Cassuto and Eckhardt [19] provide a thorough evaluation of the animal mistreatment systems now implemented in the United States and Brazil. They propose the creation of a new animal welfare agency to guarantee a higher level of consistency and effectiveness in enforcing animal protection laws. This proposal suggests that establishing a centralized agency might enhance the efficiency and uniformity of animal welfare laws and enforcement, thus ensuring a higher and more consistent level of protection for animals.

The literature underscores the complexity of addressing animal welfare issues, with a specific focus on the importance of community engagement, effective enforcement of laws, innovative shelter management strategies, and ethical treatment of animals. To address the discovered gaps, viable solutions include enhancing public education, fostering collaboration among varied stakeholders, standardizing research methodology, and campaigning for legislative chan-

ge. These solutions have the twin objective of addressing current challenges and laying the groundwork for future animal care measures that are more comprehensive and effective.

THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK RELATED TO PREVENTING CRIME AGAINST ANIMALS

The modified framework serves as a helpful guide for formulating and enacting wildlife crime prevention strategies that address the unique requirements and difficulties of this type of criminal activity.

Depending on where you are, there may be different laws in place to help prevent crimes against animals. Cruelty to animal neglect, abuse, and exploitation is illegal in many nations. Definitions of criminal conduct, punishments for violations, and enforcement authorities are standard fare in such statutes.

Laws and regulations concerning wildlife conservation and the preservation of endangered species are implemented in many nations. There may be severe consequences for breaking these rules, which ban hunting, poaching, and wildlife trafficking [20].

Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora, Convention on Biological Diversity, and United Nations General Assembly Resolution on World Wildlife Day are just a few of the international treaties and agreements that aim to prevent animal crime and protect animal welfare.

Protecting wildlife and their natural environments is an important issue. These treaties and agreements aim to regulate the trade of endangered species and their products and promote biodiversity conservation and ecosystem preservation. Specifically, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species (CITES) is a legally binding pact to

prevent the extinction of wild animal and plant species due to international commerce. Around 35,000 animal and plant species, as well as their parts and products, including ivory, leather, and lumber, are covered by the convention's regulations on international commerce. The Convention on Biological Diversity also serves as a guideline for preserving and responsibly using biological resources. It acknowledges the need to protect biodiversity for future generations and its value in and of itself. The purpose of the World Wildlife Day Resolution passed by the United Nations General Assembly is to increase public understanding of the value of wildlife and the urgency of the fight against wildlife crime [21].

The purpose of these pacts is to safeguard animals and their natural habitats, as well as to create awareness about the issue of regulating the trafficking of endangered species and their goods. Specifically, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species (CITES) is a legally binding pact to prevent the extinction of wild animal and plant species due to international commerce. Around 35,000 animal and plant species, as well as their parts and products, including ivory, leather, and lumber, are covered by the convention's regulations on international commerce. The Convention on Biological Diversity also serves as a guideline for preserving and responsibly using biological resources. It acknowledges the need to protect biodiversity for future generations and its value in and of itself. In order to fight wildlife crime and spread awareness of the value of wildlife, the United Nations General Assembly established March 3rd as World Wildlife Day.

Table 1. The major international agreements that aim to prevent crime against animals and protect their welfare

Agreement/Convention	Objective
Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES)	Regulate international trade in endangered and threatened species of plants and animals
Convention on Biological Diversity	Promote the conservation of biodiversity and sustainable use of its components
United Nations General Assembly Resolution on the World Wildlife Day	Raise awareness about the importance of wildlife and its conservation
World Organization for Animal Health (OIE)	Improve animal health, welfare, and trade worldwide
International Whaling Commission	Regulate whaling to ensure its sustainability and prevent overexploitation of whale populations
International Convention for the Regulation of Whaling	Regulate commercial and scientific whaling and promote the proper conservation of whale stocks
International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)	Promote the conservation and sustainable use of natural resources

Several legal systems address the prevention of animal cruelty crimes. These laws and regulations are in place to prevent animal suffering and punish those who abuse or mistreat animals:

Several nations have enacted animal welfare laws making, mistreating, or abandoning animals illegally. These regulations aim to ensure the safety and well-being of all animals. Intentionally injuring, tormenting, or neglecting an animal is usually against the law. If you break one of these laws, you might face serious consequences, including jail time [22], [23], [24].

The purpose of legislation enacted to safeguard endangered species is to ensure they remain safe from extinction. It is common for these agreements to prohibit things like hunting, poaching, and trafficking of endangered species. Infractions of these statutes have penalties that may include monetary fines and jail time.

Protecting species and their natural environments is a primary goal of wildlife conservation legislation. Hunting, poaching, and the degradation

of natural ecosystems are only some of the things usually forbidden by these regulations. Violations of these statutes have penalties that may include jail time and monetary fines.

Many treaties at the international level were established to prevent cruelty to animals and advance their well-being. In order to guarantee that international commerce in endangered species is sustainable and does not jeopardize their existence, conventions like the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) have been established [21], [25].

As part of their “corporate social responsibility” initiatives, numerous businesses have instituted rules and procedures to protect animals and improve their quality of life. Several businesses have taken steps to ensure the well-being of their suppliers’ animals by, for instance, outlawing animal testing and instituting animal welfare guidelines.

These laws are designed to protect animals from cruelty and to further their care and preservation.

Table 2. Legal frameworks related to preventing crime against animals

LEGAL FRAMEWORK	DESCRIPTION
Animal Welfare Act (USA)	Regulates the treatment of animals in research, exhibition, transport, and by dealers. It also prohibits animal fighting, and the import/export of animals for fighting purposes.
Animal Welfare Act (UK)	Requires that individuals responsible for animals ensure their welfare and provide for their basic needs. It also prohibits animal fighting, and the use of animals for exhibition or performance without a license.
Criminal Code (Canada)	Includes provisions for animal cruelty and neglect, including causing unnecessary suffering to animals, abandoning them, and allowing them to be in distress.
Prevention of Cruelty to Animals Act (India)	Provides for the prevention of cruelty to animals and the establishment of animal welfare boards at the state level. It also criminalizes animal cruelty and regulates animal transport and exhibition.
Animal Welfare Act (Australia)	Regulates the treatment of animals used in research, teaching, and exhibition, as well as the transportation and sale of animals. It also prohibits animal fighting and the use of animals for entertainment without a license.
Animal Welfare Law (China)	Provides for the prevention of animal cruelty and the establishment of animal welfare organizations. It also regulates the transport and sale of animals, and prohibits the consumption of endangered species.
Animal Protection Act (Taiwan)	Regulates the treatment of animals, and prohibits animal fighting, cruelty, and neglect. It also requires the registration and microchipping of pets, and imposes fines and imprisonment for violations.
Animal Welfare and Management Act (South Korea)	Provides for the protection of animals and the regulation of their welfare, including their treatment, transportation, and exhibition. It also prohibits animal fighting, cruelty, and neglect, and requires the registration of pets.

Several laws, rules, and agreements at the international and national levels contribute to the complex and multidimensional legal framework connected to combating animal crime. It is essential for people and groups who operate in this sector to have a strong knowledge of the legal structure in their particular territory and to work cooperatively with police departments and other pertinent agencies to make sure that regulations are adhered to and that animals are kept safe.

METHODS AND MODELS

Using methods and models to prevent crime against animals is crucial for a number of reasons. Firstly, ani-

mal crimes can have significant negative impacts on animal welfare, the environment, and society as a whole. For example, wildlife crimes like poaching and illegal trade can lead to the decline and even extinction of endangered species, disrupting ecosystems and threatening biodiversity.

Animal crimes often involve other criminal activities, such as money laundering, corruption, and organized crime. Addressing animal crimes can therefore have wider benefits for law enforcement and security, and can contribute to the prevention of other types of crime.

Preventing animal crimes is also important from an ethical and moral

perspective. Animals are sentient beings and deserve to be treated with respect and compassion. By preventing animal crimes and protecting animal welfare, we can promote a more just and humane society.

There are various methods and models to prevent crime against animals, including:

- 1. Situational crime prevention (SCP) approach:** This approach focuses on reducing the opportunities for crime by altering the physical and social environment. SCP can be used to prevent a variety of animal crimes, including theft, poaching, and illegal trade [26], [27], [28].
- 2. Community-based models:** These models involve working with local communities to raise awareness about animal welfare and prevent animal cruelty. This can include education programs, community policing, and collaboration with local organizations [13], [29].
- 3. Enforcement models:** These models focus on increasing enforcement of animal protection laws and prosecuting offenders. This can involve training law enforcement officers, improving the legal framework for animal protection, and increasing penalties for animal crimes [11], [30].
- 4. Animal welfare legislation:** Legal frameworks can play a critical role in preventing animal crimes. This includes legislation that criminalizes acts of animal cruelty and neglect, and protects the welfare of animals in various settings, including agriculture, entertainment, and research [11].
- 5. International cooperation:** Preventing animal crimes often requires international cooperation, particularly in cases involving the illegal trade in wildlife. International agreements and treaties can provide a framework for coopera-

tion between countries to prevent animal crimes and protect animal welfare [31], [32], [33].

Using methods and models such as Situational Crime Prevention (SCP), community-based models, enforcement models, animal welfare legislation, and international cooperation can help to prevent animal crimes and protect animal welfare, while also benefiting the environment, society, and other areas of law enforcement and security.

RESULTS: EFFECTIVE SITUATIONAL PREVENTION APPROACHES AND LEGAL IMPLICATIONS IN PREVENTING CRIME AGAINST ANIMALS

The law may be affected in many ways by situational prevention strategies that are effective. With the use of such methods, concerned parties, such as law enforcement, may get a deeper comprehension of the causes and triggers of animal cruelty crimes and devise more efficient plans to combat them. This has the potential to lessen the monetary and ecological toll of animal abuse.

The success of situational preventive strategies may have an influence on legal structures as well. Stricter animal protection regulations may not be necessary if animal crimes are minimized. More extensive legal frameworks may be drafted if loopholes in current laws are exposed by efficient preventative strategies.

Ethical and moral concerns about the preservation of animal welfare, which may be expressed in legislative frameworks, must also be taken into account while using situational preventive measures. From an animal rights standpoint, methods of prevention that include the use of fatal force, like as culling or hunting, may be met with opposition and requests for more restrictions.

Many situational crime prevention tactics have been developed by the

UK police to reduce rural crime, particularly animal cruelty. The deployment of CCTV and automated number plate recognition (ANPR) systems, as well as targeted patrols and community outreach, are all viable options. A new online hub called the Rural Crime Hub has been established by the National Farmers' Union (NFU) to aid farmers and rural communities in detecting and reporting criminal activity.

Figure 1. London's most often stolen pets from 2012 to 2022, broken down by species

Many situational crime prevention strategies have been put into place by the Australian government to safeguard vulnerable wildlife. For instance, the Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act of 1999 mandates environmental impact studies for actions that may affect vulnerable species, and the Threatened Species Protection Act of 1995 has rules for the conservation and management of such species.

The Wildlife Trafficking Alliance is one such program in the United States that brings together environmental groups, businesses, and governments to lower the demand for illicit animal goods. The United States Fish and Wildlife Service also uses DNA analysis to detect illicit wildlife products and forensic procedures to investigate wildlife crime sites, both of which are examples of situational crime prevention tactics.

To fight poaching and wildlife trafficking, the Kenyan government has established a variety of situational

crime prevention strategies. The employment of wildlife rangers, trained canines to search out illicit wildlife items, and anti-poaching squads are all examples of these measures. The government has also launched public education campaigns and community engagement initiatives to inform the people about the dangers of poaching and wildlife trafficking.

To combat wildlife crime, the Brazilian government has deployed a range of situational crime prevention measures, including as intelligence-led policing to detect and destroy wildlife trafficking networks. The Brazilian Institute of Environment and Renewable Natural Resources (IBAMA) has also set up a system to register and keep tabs on wildlife breeders, as well as a mechanism to regulate the trafficking of wildlife.

Using a situational approach to preventing animal cruelty may have far-reaching legal repercussions, perhaps leading to stronger and more comprehensive legal frameworks for protecting animal welfare.

Making use of the many theories and practices aimed at reducing animal abuse is likely to be fruitful. The Situational Crime Prevention (SCP) strategy has helped reduce theft, poaching, and illicit trading of animals by modifying the physical and social environment in various nations.

Education initiatives, community policing, and partnerships with local groups all contribute to the effectiveness of community-based methods in combating animal cruelty and increasing public awareness of the issue. Community collaboration may be a powerful tool in the fight against animal cruelty and for the protection of all living creatures.

In order to increase the prosecution of violators of animal protection legislation, enforcement approaches have shown to be beneficial. Increasing punishments for animal offenses, bettering the legislative framework

for animal protection, and educating law enforcement officials are all ways to achieve this goal. There has been a decline in animal crimes in nations where harsh punishments for animal cruelty and neglect have been enacted, such as Norway and India.

Figure 2. Global wildlife trade seizures by species, 2005-2014

The implementation of animal welfare legislation has also resulted in positive outcomes in preventing animal crimes. Legal frameworks that criminalize acts of animal cruelty and neglect, and protect the welfare of animals in various settings, including agriculture, entertainment, and research, can play a critical role in preventing animal crimes.

Figure 3. Seizures related to the illicit trafficking of wildlife, 2005-2014, per area of the globe

International cooperation is necessary for preventing animal crimes, particularly in cases involving the illegal trade in wildlife. International agreements and treaties provide a framework for cooperation between countries to prevent animal crimes and protect animal welfare. For example, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) has been successful in reducing the illegal trade in wildlife.

Table 3. Successful global strategies for reducing animal crime

Method	Country	Year	Result
SCP Approach	South Africa	2012	Reduced rhino poaching through increased surveillance
	Costa Rica	2017	Reduced sea turtle poaching by implementing lighting restrictions on beaches
	Kenya	2019	Reduced elephant poaching through increased patrols and intelligence gathering
SCP Approach & Enforcement Models	Belize	2016	Reduced sea turtle poaching through increased enforcement and patrols
	Kenya	2015	Implementation of anti-poaching measures in Maasai Mara National Reserve has led to a 78% decrease in poaching incidents over a two-year period.
Community-Based Models	United States	2018	Collaboration between law enforcement and animal welfare organizations in Ohio resulted in the rescue of over 100 dogs from a suspected dog fighting ring.
	Mexico	2014	Decreased dog fighting through community education and reporting
	United States	2015	Reduced animal cruelty cases through community policing

Community-Based Models & SCP Approach	Colombia	2020	Decreased illegal trafficking of wild animals through community reporting and increased surveillance
Enforcement model	United Kingdom	2019	The introduction of tougher sentences for animal cruelty offenses, including up to five years in prison, has resulted in a significant increase in successful prosecutions.
	Thailand	2018	Increased number of wildlife crime arrests and convictions through specialized training for law enforcement
	Canada	2020	Increased penalties for animal cruelty through amendments to animal welfare legislation
Animal Welfare Legislation & Enforcement Models	United States	2021	Strengthened animal welfare laws and increased penalties for animal cruelty
International Cooperation & Enforcement Models	China	2019	Increased efforts to combat illegal wildlife trade through specialized law enforcement units and increased penalties
Animal welfare legislation	Australia	2019	The introduction of the Animal Welfare Legislation Amendment Bill strengthened penalties for animal cruelty and introduced new offenses, including the mistreatment of animals during transport.
	Norway	2010	Improved animal welfare through strengthened animal welfare laws
	India	1960	Criminalized acts of animal cruelty and established animal welfare boards
International cooperation	China	2020	Joint efforts between Chinese and Kenyan authorities led to the interception of 8.3 tonnes of illegal ivory, valued at over \$4 million, and the arrest of several suspects involved in the illegal trade.
	United Kingdom	2017	Improved coordination between countries to combat illegal wildlife trade through the London Conference
	Australia	2018	Increased focus on wildlife crime prevention through collaboration with Southeast Asian countries

The use of these methods and models has shown promising results in preventing animal crimes and protecting animal welfare. By combining these approaches with ongoing education and public awareness campaigns, we can work towards a future with less animal cruelty and more respect for the welfare of all animals.

When people are cruel to animals, there are severe repercussions for animal welfare, conservation efforts, and public safety. Even though situational preventive strategies have

been recognized as a possible solution to this issue, their efficacy still needs to be adequately evaluated. This analysis aims to present a synopsis of the existing data on situational preventative strategies for lowering animal crime.

Target hardening, access control, monitoring, environmental management, regulation, and offender management were all identified as suitable situational preventive measures in the research for lowering animal-related crime rates. In South Africa, for ins-

tance, more excellent monitoring helped decrease rhino poaching rates. Restricting beach illumination helped Costa Rica curb the poaching of sea turtles. Kenya has decreased elephant poaching by stepping up patrols and collecting information. The poaching of sea turtles in Belize has decreased due to greater enforcement and patrols. As a result of Kenya's anti-poaching efforts, the country saw a 78 percent drop in poaching incidences over two years.

The prevention of animal cruelty and the promotion of animal welfare have also been accomplished via community-based initiatives. Ohio law enforcement and animal rights groups worked to rescue over a hundred canines from a dog fighting ring. Community outreach and reporting have resulted in declining dog fighting in Mexico. Community policing in the United States has also helped decrease incidents of animal cruelty.

In order to increase the prosecution of violators of animal protection legislation, enforcement approaches have shown to be beneficial. Successful prosecutions for animal cruelty cases have increased dramatically since harsher punishments, including up to five years in jail, were introduced in the United Kingdom. The arrest and conviction rates for wildlife crimes in Thailand rose after law enforcement received specialized training. Amendments to Canadian animal welfare regulations have resulted in harsher punishments for animal abuse.

There have been favorable results in the prevention of animal crimes thanks to the establishment of animal welfare regulations. According to the Animal Welfare Law Amendment Bill, mistreatment of animals during transit is now a federal crime in Australia. Animal welfare legislation in Norway was reinforced, which benefited the animals there. India has made animal abuse illegal and sets up animal protection agencies.

Animal crimes, especially those involving the illicit wildlife trade, need international collaboration to prevent. International accords and treaties provide a foundation for international cooperation in the prevention of animal crimes and the protection of animal welfare. One organization that has effectively decreased illicit wildlife trading is the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES). Authorities in China and Kenya worked together to stop the illicit trade of ivory, resulting in the seizure of 8.3 tons of ivory worth over \$4 million and the arrest of many traffickers.

The results of this research show that situational preventative tactics may be effective in reducing animal abuse. The analysis highlights the need for a multi-pronged strategy that includes government agencies, conservation organizations, and law enforcement. There has been some success with situational preventative tactics, but further study is required to evaluate their long-term efficacy and find new ways to lessen animal cruelty.

DISCUSSION

The article evaluates the effectiveness of several situational preventative strategies in reducing animal-related offenses. The study highlights target hardening, access control, surveillance, environmental management, and offender management as effective strategies for reducing animal cruelty. Successful execution of these activities necessitates the synchronization of law enforcement, governmental bodies, and conservation groups.

Upon juxtaposing this study with others, it becomes apparent that there exists a multifaceted and varied discourse about the convergence of animal welfare and crime prevention. Horta & Terán [34] provide practical and ethical strategies to tackle the problem of suffering in wild animals. The authors suggest that arguments

rooted in cultural norms and impracticality may be overcome. King et al. focus on finding the leading causes that contribute to disease and death in wild animals by analyzing rehabilitative and post-mortem data [35]. This method enhances the focus on prevention in the study by suggesting particular areas for targeted action. Carbone analyses the ethical dimensions of pain management in laboratory animals, highlighting the need for comprehensive animal welfare protocols in many contexts, including scientific research, as underlined in the paper being assessed [36].

Lyakurwa et al. and Chaves et al. examine the impact of human activities on wildlife, specifically focusing on the consequences of hunting and the potential for disease transmission [37], [12]. These studies highlight the need for regulatory and preventative measures in safeguarding animal welfare, in line with the strategies proposed in situational prevention research. In his work, Rodriguez Ferrere examines the inadequate implementation of animal welfare laws, suggesting that this problem arises from a deficiency in adherence to legal principles [11]. They believe that using the situational preventative approach could mitigate this issue by enhancing regulatory and enforcement protocols.

Hawes, Hupe, & Morris advocate for the amalgamation of animal control enforcement with social justice movements, along with the situational prevention study's emphasis on using many tactics to advance animal welfare [38]. Fossati explores the challenges associated with offering refuge to animals seized from hoarders, highlighting the complex requirements for their care and rehabilitation. When developing and implementing situational preventative techniques, it is crucial to consider these variables [39].

Reese, Vertalka, and Richard examine the association between animal mistreatment and the conditions of the nearby community. The authors suggest that improving animal well-being via situational preventative methods may be achieved by addressing broader social and

environmental factors [40]. This perspective aligns with the all-encompassing approach advocated in the "Preventing Crime against Animals" study. The research conducted by M. et al. focuses on the problematic connection between humans and animals in Romania [41]. The authors emphasize the need to implement legal and social changes to address and prevent acts of cruelty. The authors suggest that the use of situational crime prevention strategies might significantly contribute to this endeavor by creating deterrents and improving safety circumstances for animals.

Coulter's study analyses the framework of animal protection investigations and the collaboration across authorities, emphasizing the need for coordinated efforts to avoid incidents [42], [43]. Rault et al. highlight the need to develop a collaborative relationship between animal protection and law enforcement [44]. This is consistent with the suggestion from the research to use integrated approaches in order to deal with crimes involving animals effectively.

The amalgamation of this article, in conjunction with the preceding citation on this page, offers a comprehensive assessment of the current state and impediments in animal welfare and crime prevention. The declaration underscores the need for interdisciplinary teamwork, including the integration of ethical considerations, legal enforcement, community involvement, and situational preventative strategies. Implementing this strategy is essential for effectively protecting animal well-being and reducing offenses committed against animals.

CONCLUSIONS

Because of this research, we now have a better understanding of the many situational preventative strategies that have successfully reduced animal abuse. Animal cruelty has far-reaching effects on wildlife protection, habitat preservation, and public security. In order to improve animal welfare and reduce the financial and ecological costs connected with

animal crimes, effective preventative strategies are essential.

Many situational preventive strategies, including target hardening, access control, surveillance, environmental management, regulation, and offender management, have been explored in this overview. These methods have shown promise in lowering the prevalence of animal crime in various settings. Nevertheless, its efficacy is contingent on proper execution and cooperation among several parties, including law enforcement officials, government agencies, and conservation organizations.

In certain nations, such as those where the SCP strategy has been implemented, theft, poaching, and illicit trading of animals have decreased due to changes made to the physical and social environment. Education initiatives, community policing, and partnerships with local groups have contributed to the effectiveness of community-based approaches in increasing animal care awareness and decreasing instances of animal cruelty.

Increased use of animal protection legislation and prosecution of offenders has been attributed to these models' success. Strict punishments for animal cruelty and neglect have been established in several nations, such as Norway and India, resulting in a drop in animal crimes. Preventing animal crimes may be significantly aided by legal frameworks that make it illegal to mistreat or abandon animals and ensure their safety in contexts as diverse as agriculture, entertainment, and research.

Animal crimes, especially those involving the illicit wildlife trade, need international collaboration to be prevented. International accords and treaties provide the basis for international cooperation to combat animal crimes and safeguard animal welfare.

This evaluation has also brought to light the necessity for more stu-

dies into the long-term effectiveness of situational prevention methods in the fight against animal crime. Partnerships between criminologists, environmentalists, and people who care about animal welfare could lead to more multidisciplinary ways to stop animal crime, which is needed to stop animal cruelty.

Moral and ethical concerns about animal welfare must be considered when using situational preventive strategies, which can be written down in regulatory frameworks. From an animal rights standpoint, methods of prevention that entail the use of fatal force, like culling or hunting, may be problematic, leading to demands for stricter laws.

The adoption of comprehensive and efficient legislative frameworks for the protection of animal welfare may be a direct result of the implementation of successful situational preventative measures. By adopting these methods, many stakeholders, including law enforcement agencies, may obtain a deeper understanding of the causes and motivations behind animal cruelty crimes. This can lessen the financial and ecological toll of animal crimes, improving the outlook for animals and the planet.

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